

THIAZOLINYLYDRAZONES. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF 4-OXO-5-(ARYL)- Δ^2 -THIAZOLIN-2-YLYDRAZONES

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α -Halo-arylacetic acids have been condensed with aryl thiosemicarbazones to obtain the 4-oxo-5-(aryl)- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones.

Buu Hoi *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 415; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 716) found 4-oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones to exhibit tuberculostatic activity. Similar compounds with an aryl group on C₅ of the hetero ring do not seem to have been studied. It seemed desirable therefore to prepare thiazolinylydrazones having an aryl group on C₅ of the hetero ring. α -Bromophenyl- and α -bromo-(*o*-chloro)-phenylacetic acids have been condensed with aryl thiosemicarbazones to yield 4-oxo-5-(phenyl/*o*-chlorophenyl)- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiosemicarbazones were prepared from aromatic aldehydes and thiosemicarbazide by the procedure of Buu Hoi *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). α -Bromoarylacetic acids were condensed with aryl thiosemicarbazones as described by Buu Hoi *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The hydrazones were obtained in 40 to 80% yield and were crystallised from acetic acid.

TABLE I

(I: X = Ph)

R=	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
1. H	260-61°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	10.8	10.9
2. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	261-62°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	10.3	10.4
3. <i>p</i> -OCH ₃	266°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.7	9.8
4. <i>p</i> -Cl	275°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	9.6	9.7
5. 2:4-Cl ₂	232°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.7	8.8
6. <i>o</i> -Cl	254°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	9.6	9.7
7. <i>o</i> -OCH ₃	228-29°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.7	9.8
8. <i>p</i> -OH	320°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.2	10.3
9. 5-Cl-2-OH	299°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	9.2	9.3
10. <i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N	277°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S	9.4	9.5
11. <i>o</i> -OH	287°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.4	10.3

TABLE II
(I: X = *o*-C₆H₄Cl)

R=	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
1. H	272°	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ ON ₂ ClS	9.6	9.7
2. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	286°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₂ ClS	9.2	9.3
3. <i>p</i> -OCH ₃	266°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	8.8	8.9
4. <i>p</i> -Cl	279°	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.9	8.8
5. 2:4-Cl ₂	276°	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.1	8.0
6. <i>o</i> -Cl	258°	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.7	8.8
7. <i>o</i> -OCH ₃	256°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	8.7	8.9
8. <i>p</i> -OH	334°	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	9.1	9.2
9. 5-Cl-2-OH	270°	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.5	8.4
10. <i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N	290°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	8.7	8.6
11. <i>o</i> -OH	290°	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	9.0	9.2

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